
A STUDY OF SOCIAL MEDIA AND INFLUENCER MARKETING EFFECTS ON ONLINE SPENDING PATTERNS OF GENERATION Z: IMPLICATIONS FOR SUSTAINABLE CONSUMPTION

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ABSTRACT

Social media has become an important part of the daily life of young people. Generation Z spends much time on different social media platforms. Many companies use influencers to recommend their products online. Influencers share reviews, recommendations, and experiences about products, which can affect the buying decisions of their followers. The main aim of this study is to understand how social media and influencer impact the online spending habits and financial behavior of Gen Z. The study is relies on both primary and secondary data. Primary data was collected with the help of a questionnaire from 130respondents from the Gen Z age group. Secondary data was compiled from books, journals, and online articles. The observation from the study shows that many young consumers are shaped by social media content and influencer recommendations during their buying decisions. It was also observed that social media sometimes leads to unplanned purchase behavior among Gen Z. The study indicates the importance of safe social media practice and financial awareness for sustainable consumption.

Keywords: *Social Media, Influencer Marketing, Online Spending Patterns, Generation Z, Online Shopping Behaviour, Impulse Buying, Sustainable consumption.*

1. INTRODUCTION

In today's digital world, social media has Impact on the way people communicate, share information, and buy products. Instagram, YouTube and other social media have become very popular among young generation. Many companies now use social media influencer to promote their products. Influencers have a notable number of followers on social media and can impact the opinions and preference of their audience. When influencer's advice a product, many followers relies on their opinion and may decide to buy that product. Generation Z is the most engaged group on social media. They often explore new brands and products with the help of influencer content. Digital Influencer plays an important role in affecting their spending behavior. However, this influence may also results in unplanned purchases and increased spending. Therefore, it is important to study how social media affects the spending and saving habit of Gen Z and how it relates to careful consumption.

Significance of the Study

This study is useful for understanding how social media influences the spending behavior of young consumers. It also helps marketers understand the responsibility they have while promoting products through influencers. The study can also create awareness among young people about managing their money and making responsible spending decisions. In addition, the study highlights the importance of promoting sustainable and responsible consumption in society.

2. REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Adaba (2025) studied the role of trust in influencer marketing and concluded that trust is a key factor that influences consumer decision-making and buying behavior.

Septiani (2025) found that influencer marketing has a significant impact on consumer behavior, but the effectiveness depends on selecting the right influencer for the target audience.

Giannakopoulos, N., & Migkos, S. (2025) concluded that influencer marketing positively impacts consumer behavior by increasing engagement and sales. However, excessive or inauthentic promotions can reduce trust and create negative reactions. Therefore, authenticity and transparency are essential for its effectiveness..

Mahajan and Garg (2026) found that factors such as credibility, trustworthiness, expertise, and authenticity of influencers have a significant impact on consumer purchase intention.

Research Gap

Most studies on social media and influencer marketing focus on consumer behavior, brand engagement, and purchase decisions. However, limited research examines their impact on the financial behavior of Generation Z,

such as spending and saving habits. Thus, a clear gap exists in understanding how social media influences Gen Z's financial responsibility.

3. Objectives of the Study

1. To study the impact of social media usage on the online spending behaviour of Gen Z.
2. To examine the influence of influencer marketing on purchase decisions of Generation Z.
3. To analyse the relationship between social media exposure and financial behaviour (spending and saving habits) of Generation Z.

4. Hypotheses of the Study

i) **H₀₁ (Null):** Social media has no significant impact on the online spending behaviour of Generation Z.

H₁₁(Alternative): Social media has a significant impact on the online spending behaviour of Generation Z.

ii) **H₀₂:** Influencer marketing does not significantly influence purchase decisions of Generation Z.

H₁₂: Influencer marketing significantly influences purchase decisions of Generation Z.

iii) **H₀₃:** There is no significant relationship between social media exposure and financial behaviour of Generation Z.

H₁₃: There is a significant relationship between social media exposure and financial behaviour of Generation Z.

5. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study follows a descriptive research design. This type of research helps in understanding the behavior and opinions of respondents regarding social media and online spending.

Sources of Data

The study is on the basis of both primary and secondary data.

Primary Data

Primary data was gathered from respondent directly from Generation Z, especially those between the ages of 18 and 28 years using a structured questionnaire.

Secondary Data

Secondary data was collected from books, academic journals, research articles, and online sources related to social media marketing and consumer behavior.

Sample Size

Generation Z includes individuals born between 1997 and 2012. This study focuses on respondents born between 1997 and 2007 (aged 18–28 years) residing in the western suburbs of Mumbai. A total of 100 respondents participated in the survey.

Data Collection

Primary data was collected through a questionnaire survey. It examines the impact of social media usage and influencer marketing on their online spending behavior. The research mainly focuses on social media users who follow influencers and shop online. The questionnaire included questions related to social media usage, following influencers, online shopping habits, and spending behavior.

6. Data Analysis and Interpretation

1. Age

Graph No. 1 Age of Respondent

Interpretation: A majority of respondents fall in the 18–20 age group which indicating that response from Gen Z in their early adulthood.

2. Gender

Graph No. 2 Gender of Respondent

Interpretation: The sample is relatively balanced, with Male and female respondents.

3. Occupation

Graph No.3 Occupation of Respondent

Interpretation: Out of 100 people, 95% are students, showing that most of the group consists of students. Only a small number of people are working professionals.

Very few people are self-employed, making it the least common occupation in the group.

Graph No.4 Use of social media

Interpretation: Out of 100 respondents, large majority of 85% respondents reported using social media daily, while 10% respondents use it a few times a week and only 5% respondents use it rarely. This clearly indicates that Gen Z is highly active on social media platforms. Such high usage shows the strong power of social media as useful medium for marketing and communication.

5. Which social media platform do you use the most?
100 responses

Graph No. 5 Social media platform

Interpretation: Among the respondents, 100 out of 80% primarily use Instagram, followed by 13% respondents selecting other platforms, 5% using Snapchat, and only 2% using Facebook. This shows that Instagram is largely the most preferred platform among Gen Z users. The influence of Instagram suggests that it is the most powerful platform for digital marketing and promotion through influencer.

6. Do you follow social media influencers?
100 responses

Graph No.6 Social media influencers

Interpretation: Out of the total respondents, 58% individuals stated that they follow social media influencers, whereas 42% respondents do not follow them. This indicates that although a majority of Gen Z users are connected to influencers, a notable portion remains independent of influencer content. Therefore, influencer marketing has reach, but it does not cover the entire audience.

7. Have you ever purchased a product after seeing it promoted by an influencer?
100 responses

Graph No.7 Impact of Influencer Promotion on Product Purchase

Interpretation: When asked about purchasing behavior, 56% respondents reported that they have not purchased products after influencer promotion; while 44% respondents accepted that they have made such purchases. This suggests that while influencers do impact consumer behavior, their power to influence decision into actual purchases is average rather than strong.

8. How much do influencer recommendations affect your buying decisions?
100 responses

Graph No.8 Effect of Influencer Recommendations on Buying Decision

Interpretation: The responses show that **35% respondents consider influencer recommendations not influential**, while **27% respondents find them partly influential**, another **24% respondent's average influential**, and only **14% respondents highly influential**. This response pattern indicates that most respondents fall within the low to moderate influence range, suggesting that Gen Z consumers are careful and do not rely heavily on influencer recommendations when making purchasing decisions.

9. What type of products do you usually buy after seeing influencer promotions?
100 responses

Graph No.9 Types of Products Purchased After Influencer Promotion

Interpretation: Among the respondents, **40% individuals purchased fashion and clothing products**, making it the most popular category. This is followed by **12% respondents purchasing beauty products**, **11% purchasing electronics**, **10% purchasing food-related items**, and **27% selecting other categories**. This indicates that influencer marketing is most effective in good looking and lifestyle-related categories such as fashion.

10. How often do you shop online?
100 responses

Graph No.10 Frequency of Online Shopping

Interpretation: Out of 100 respondents, **48% reported that they shop online sometimes**, while **38% respondents shop rarely**, and only **14% respondents shop frequently**. This shows that most Gen Z users engage in online shopping occasionally rather than regularly, reflecting controlled and need-based purchasing behavior.

11. Do you think influencers should promote responsible and sustainable products?
100 responses

Graph No.11 Opinion on Influencers Promoting Responsible and Sustainable Products

Interpretation: The data reveals that **51% respondents spend less than ₹1000 per month, 29% respondents spend between ₹1000 and ₹3000, and only 20% respondents spend more than ₹3000.** This indicates that the majority of Gen Z consumers maintain relatively low spending levels, showing budget-conscious financial behavior.

12. Do you sometimes buy products impulsively after seeing them on social media?
100 responses

Graph No.12 Impulse Buying After Seeing Products on Social Media

Interpretation: The responses show that **43% respondents do not make impulse purchases, while 31% respondents sometimes engage in impulse buying, and 26% respondents admit that they do make such purchases.** This suggests that while impulse buying exists among Gen Z, it is not a leading behavior, and many users remain aware of their spending decisions.

13. Do you think social media influences your spending habits?
100 responses

Graph No.13 Impact of Social Media on Spending Habits

Interpretation: Out of the respondents, **39% individuals stated that social media sometimes affects their spending habits, while 34% respondents said yes, and 27% respondents said no.** This indicates that social media has average influence on spending behavior, affecting users sometime rather than regularly.

14. Do you usually plan your budget before online shopping?
100 responses

Graph No.14 Budget Planning Before Shopping

Interpretation: The data shows that **56% respondents plan their budget before shopping**, while **29% respondents do so sometimes**, and only **15% respondents do not plan at all**. This proves that most Gen Z consumers are financially aware and practice budgeting, even though they are subjected to social media and influencer marketing.

15. Do you think influencers should promote responsible and sustainable products?
100 responses

Graph No.15 Influencers Should Promote Responsible and Sustainable Products

Interpretation: A majority of **53% respondents believe that influencers should promote sustainable products**, while **34% respondents think they should sometimes do so**, and only **13% respondents disagreed**. This highlights a strong inclination among Gen Z towards sustainability and ethical consumption, emphasizing the importance of responsible influencer marketing.

7. LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY

1. The results are based on the perception and responses of the participants.
2. The study focuses on Gen Z consumers and may not represent the behavior of other age groups.
3. Time restrictions also impose restriction on scope of the research.

8. FINDINGS OF THE STUDY

The study found that social media plays an important role in shaping the behaviour and lifestyle of Generation Z. A large number of respondents (86 out of 100) use social media daily, which indicates a high level of digital engagement. Instagram emerged as the most favoured platform, with 78 respondents using it the most, making it the leading platform for influencer marketing.

The study found that 61 respondents follow influencers, indicating that influencer marketing has considerable reach among Gen Z. However, only 44 respondents said they purchased products after influencer promotion, while 56 respondents did not, showing that influencer impact on actual purchase decisions is moderate, not strong. It was also noted that most respondents (32 not influenced, 27 slightly influenced, and 27 moderately influenced) fall in the low to moderate influence category. This suggests that Gen Z consumers are aware and selective in their decision-making process. In terms of spending behavior, most respondents (53 out of 100) spend less than ₹1000 per month, indicating cost-responsible behavior. Additionally, 56 respondents plan their budget before shopping, showing financial awareness. Whereas impulse buying exists (25 respondents), it does not play a major role, as many respondents either avoid it or do it occasionally. The study also highlights that 52 respondents believe influencers should promote sustainable products, reflecting an increased sense of social responsibility and value-based consumption among Gen Z.

9. RECOMMENDATIONS

1. Influencers should provide honest reviews and genuine opinions, as Gen Z consumers are aware and do not easily trust misleading promotions.
2. Brands and influencers should promote eco-friendly and socially responsible products, as a majority of respondents support sustainable consumption.
3. Since Instagram is the most preferred platform marketers should focus more on Instagram-based campaigns for better reach and engagement.
4. Educational initiatives should be introduced to help young consumers manage their finances and avoid unnecessary spending.
5. Micro-influencers often have stronger engagement and trust among followers, making them more effective for influencing purchase decisions.
6. Marketers should avoid excessive pressure tactics and instead focus on informative and value-based promotion strategies.
7. While fashion products dominate, brands should also promote other essential categories like electronics and daily-use items in a responsible manner.

10. CONCLUSION

Based on the findings of the study, it can be determined that social media and influencer marketing have a noticeable but controlled influence on the online spending behavior of Generation Z. While social media platforms, especially Instagram, play an important role in shaping awareness and preferences, their impact on actual purchasing decisions is moderate.

Generation Z is highly active on social media, yet they demonstrate financially responsible behavior. Most respondents prefer budgeting, controlled spending, and careful decision-making rather than impulsive buying. This indicates that Gen Z consumers are not blindly influenced by social media but instead act as informed and rational buyers.

Furthermore, the study shows a positive inclination towards sustainable consumption, as many respondents expect influencers to promote ethical and environmentally friendly products. This highlights the importance of responsible influencer marketing in today's digital environment.

Overall, social media acts as an influential factor but not a dominant force in determining financial behavior. A balance exists between digital influence and financial awareness among Gen Z consumers.

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